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QR CODE READING APP

ABSTRACT:The current DSS tools are generally built as “desktop applications” and designed for the use of data mining experts. In this paper, design and implementation of ASMINER, a new web-based data mining exploration and reporting tool, is introduced. ASMINER enables both decision makers and also knowledge workers, exploring and reporting with three data mining techniques (decision trees, clustering and association rules mining), by presenting a scalable, user-friendly and fully web-based thin client data mining tool. The approach and the tools of ASMINER have a significant potential at giving an opportunity to knowledge workers to participate in decision making phases.

KEY WORD : ASMINER,DESKTOP,DATA MINING,QR CODE

INTRODUCTION:A QR code is a type of matrix bar code or two-dimensional code that can store data information and designed to be read by smartphones. QR stands for “Quick Response” indicating that the code contents should be decoded very quickly at high speed. The code consists of black modules arranged in a square pattern on a white background. The information encoded may be text, a URL or other data [1] [2]. The QR code was designed to allow its contents to be decoded at high speed. The popularity of QR codes is growing rapidly all around the world. Nowadays, mobile phones with built-in camera are widely used to recognize the QR Codes.

QR Codes are created by the Toyota subsidiary Denso Wave in 1994, and was initially used for tracking inventory in vehicle parts manufacturing. The idea behind the development of the QR code is the limitation of the barcode information capacity (can only hold 20 alphanumeric characters).

While they are developed for tracking parts in vehicle manufacturing, QR codes now are used in many other fields, from commercial tracking to entertainment, in-store product labeling, and in

those applications that are aimed at smartphone users. Users may open URL; receive text after scanning QR codes. By using QR code generating sites or apps, users can generate and print their own QR codes for others to scan and use.

The QR code system consists of a QR code encoder and decoder. The encoder is responsible for encoding data and generation of the QR Code, while the decoder decodes the data from the QR code.

SYSTEM STUDY:Encoding region contains format information, version information, data and error correction codes. For format information, one-module array must be reserved near the top-left, top-right, bottom-left finder pattern and version information, an area of a 6×3 block above the bottom-left finder pattern and a 3×6 block to the left of the top-right finder pattern is reserved.

EXISTING SYSTEM : A QR code encodes a string of text. The QR standard has four modes for encoding text: numeric, alphanumeric, byte, and Kanji. Each mode encodes the text as a string of bits (1s and 0s), but each mode uses a different method for converting the text into bits, and each encoding method is optimized to encode the data with the shortest possible string of bits. Therefore, first step should be to perform data analysis to determine whether text can be encoded in numeric, alphanumeric, byte, or Kanji mode, and then select the most optimal mode for your text.

FILE DESIGN:Certain patterns in the QR code matrix can make it difficult for QR code scanners to correctly read the code. To counteract this, the QR code specification defines eight mask patterns, each of which alters the QR code according to a particular pattern.

Android Studio Using Java:

Android Studio is a powerful Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for developing Android applications, and it uses Java as its primary programming language. Java is used to write the code for the Android application, while Android Studio provides the tools and features necessary to build, test, and deploy the application.

When creating an Android project in Android Studio, Java is the default programming language, but Kotlin, another programming language, is also supported. Java provides a wide range of

features and libraries that are useful for developing Android applications, such as its robust object-oriented programming capabilities, its extensive class libraries, and its ability to handle multithreading.

One of the primary benefits of using Java for Android development is its cross-platform capabilities. Since Java can run on any system that has a Java Virtual Machine (JVM) installed, developers can write code once and then deploy it on multiple platforms. This feature is particularly useful for Android development since there are so many different devices and operating systems to consider.

CONCLUSION :In conclusion, the Android QR code scanner project is a useful and practical application that allows users to scan and decode QR codes using their Android devices. It can be used in a variety of settings, including retail, marketing, transportation, and more.

Through this project, we learned how to implement QR code scanning functionality in an Android app using the ZXing library. We also learned about the different types of QR codes and their use cases, as well as how to handle exceptions and errors that may occur during the scanning process.

Overall, the Android QR code scanner project is a valuable addition to any developer's portfolio and can be customized and extended to meet the specific needs of different industries and businesses

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